

THE INTEGRATION OF ARTS IN THE GENERAL EDUCATION COURSE OF HIGHER EDUCATION

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 20

Issue 9

Pages: 1155-1162

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1920

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11664884

Manuscript Accepted: 05-09-2024

The Integration of Arts in the General Education Course of Higher Education

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Abstract

In the higher education institutions, "arts integration" as a teaching method refers to the integration of artistic practices and activities within general education courses. Arts integration is not only about teaching art as a subject, but rather, this technique integrates creative teachings, activities, and experiences into the subject matter that all students, regardless of their major, generally encounter. This research explores the impact and perceptions of students when it comes to the integration of arts in the general education course of higher education. The researchers used a descriptive-correlational research design that investigates the impact of integrating various art forms into the general education course or non-artistic subjects to recognize its potential to develop the students' holistic well-being. It highlights how arts may support more inclusive and engaging learning environments that embrace a diversity of intelligences and learning styles. A purposive sampling technique was used in data gathering because the respondents were all the teacher education students enrolled in Art Appreciation. In determining the significant difference in the perception of the respondents based on their demographic profile, the statistical tool used was t-test. The findings of the study reveals a high level of satisfaction with the teaching strategies employed in the Art Appreciation course, and the students have a positive perception of the impact of arts integration in their learning domains. Therefore, teachers and curriculum designers should include art-based instruction and assessments that allow students to freely express themselves while ensuring its alignment with the subject matter. Policymakers in higher education should promote arts integration, recognizing its role in enhancing student learning experiences, and overall academic performance.

Keywords: *arts integration, arts in general education course, art-based instruction, integration of arts, impact of arts, general education course*

Introduction

The integration of arts in classroom instruction has been an ongoing discussion. Since it takes a lot of time and resources, some teachers consider it challenging, which explains why most of them remain in a normal classroom setting. Students experience passive learning when they rely on the teachers to convey the information, which may cause them to be less interested and inattentive, have less involvement in a high-quality learning experience, or tend to be shy when they are not given the opportunity to express their own ideas.

A study about the "Integrated Art-based Teaching Model for Brain-based Learning" by Inocian (2015) reveals that the participants of the K to 12 training for Grade 10 social studies teachers have insufficient skills in the integration of creativity which needs utmost attention. This emphasize that teachers are proficient in providing knowledge and enhancing the skills of the students who exercise only the left side of their brain. However, the right side of the brain is not well sustained, which is generally associated with creativity, spatial awareness, intuition, emotions, and holistic thinking. The integration of arts in classroom instruction will serve as the vehicle for learning and to foster the child's three learning domain that will help them reach their full human potential.

In the Philippines, the study of the arts is seen as an important part of the curriculum. Some schools offer programs in any variety of artistic fields; therefore, children can discover and improve their creativity and artistic skills. Philippine artists value art through the creation and preservation of the country's identity and culture. In order to inspire and provide knowledge, Filipino artists share works of art, whether their own or those created by others. They utilize art to express stories that promote empathy for others, enthusiasm, and cross-cultural perspectives.

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED under the new curriculum included the course of Art Appreciation on its General Education courses which is common to all programs in the bachelor level. The new curriculum is an Outcome-based education (OBE) which is an educational trend that transformed the traditional approach in teaching to transformational. Fernando (2021) conducted research about OBE and mentioned that OBE also focuses on the performance and demonstration of learners' mastery within a period. Having a decade of experience in teaching in the higher education, she explored on the right teaching methodology and approach that could achieve the Outcome-based Education. She manages teacher education program and have evaluated numerous methodologies for effective teaching and learning. Integration of arts is one of the methodologies used inside the classroom to incorporate students creativity while their critical thinking skills are being developed. The description provided for the Art Appreciation is that it develops the students' ability to appreciate, analyze, and critique works of art, which provides students with a broad knowledge of the practical, historical, and philosophical relevance of arts and provides opportunities to explore the diversity and rootedness of Filipino culture. The Art Appreciation Course is one of the general education courses that fosters students' understanding and appreciation of artistic expression. CHED ensures that the Art Appreciation course allows students to explore the diversity and unique artistic expressions of individuals, which promotes an understanding and appreciation of Filipino culture.

Art integration is the key to the success of students in higher education since it stimulates the learner's creativity and provides different

ways of understanding complex concepts. Since art has various forms, it identifies the students' learning styles and unique intelligence, which allows them to have successful learning in a particular subject. They utilize artistic disciplines to provide support and enhance the content in other subject areas (Heiman, 2020). When the arts are used to support curricular lessons, it is possible to enhance a student's understanding of the curricular content as well as deepen abstract thinking skills (Catterall, 2002).

Art is defined as a broad diversity of human activity that applies creativity and expression. Art integration in classroom instruction is a teaching approach that any teacher in different ages, subjects, and schools can apply to various art forms that the students' can use as their tools for learning. According to Hayes and Clark (2017), when the arts are integrated inside the classroom, it encourages creativity and effective learning through multiple methods while the students enjoy the learning process. Art is classified based on the type of medium and the types of media: visual and performing art (Fatma, 2018). These types of art forms can be integrated into learning activities and assessments to support each student's learning style. Classroom diversity is prominent, and it fosters a sense of individuality and self-expression among students. By integrating arts in their educational experiences, they can convey their ideas and emotions that deepens their empathy for their peers and understanding of the world around them.

The general education course in higher education provides a broad range of knowledge in various fields. However, students' learning experiences sometimes lead to passive learning with less engagement. Educators of higher education are encouraged to incorporate various art forms into their instruction and assessment methods. This research aims to investigate the impact of integrating the arts into instruction and assessment on the students' learning process by examining their perceptions of the teaching strategies and learning activities employed in the Art Appreciation course.

Research Questions

This study aims to identify the impact and perception of the respondents on the integration of arts in the general education course of higher education. Specifically, this study attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of satisfaction of the respondents on the teaching strategies employed in the Art Appreciation course?
2. What is the impact of the integration of arts in the general education course of higher education as perceived by the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. cognitive development;
 - 1.2. affective development; and
 - 1.3. psychomotor development?
3. Is there a significant difference on the perceptions of the respondents on the integration of arts in the general education course of higher education when grouped according to profile?

Literature Review

The integration of arts in the general education of higher education encourages students to recognize its benefits and how it can impact their development that can improve their learning. According to Hasan et al. (2022), art is closely connected to technology and engineering, inspiring creativity to improve learners' experiences and visually convey ideas, emphasizing its potential role at various stages of the problem-solving process. Arts must be implemented in various ways throughout the problem-solving processes. The holistic integration of art can lead to more innovative and effective solutions. The integration of arts in classroom settings serves as an Art-based instruction, meaning the teacher's creativity through the use of art forms foster learning in other non-artistic subject matters. Making the subject matter experiential is one of the best methods to excel, and art integration is the ideal option (Kaur & Ansari, 2023). Art integration engages students in experiential learning activities that allow them to better understand what they are learning. Teachers must focus on what knowledge, values, and skills they want the students to learn based on the lesson's objectives and select an activity and strategy of integration to address or perform these skills (Heiman, 2020). To integrate art into our instruction, we must first understand the objectives of our lesson, and with the help of the objectives, we can be creative using any art forms that will impact the students' learning domains.

Arts integration into the curriculum has a positive impact on the student's engagement, motivation, and perseverance since students interact with the content and materials using both their minds and bodies (Zhou & Brown, 2018). Art-based instruction engages students in body movements and mind coordination, through which they gain ways to express their knowledge and ideas through collaborating and solving problems with their peers. According to Karkou et al. (2022), studies combining artistic disciplines with therapies reveal that using various art forms can help improve the well-being of both students and teachers, showing a positive impact on both physical and emotional health. This suggests that the arts aren't just about brain development; it also impact our physical and emotional well-being.

Students in the 2020 study reported that the incorporation of the arts-based teaching and learning approaches helped them to sustain an interest in the course material (Hunter & Frawley, 2022). The art-based teaching strategy had a positive impact that maintained the interest and participation of the students in the learning process. Arts integrated instruction fostered environments in which students reported increased self-efficacy and self-esteem. Art-based learning activities implemented by the teacher engage students to explore at their own pace, fostering enjoyment and the development of their social skills and self-control (Casciano et al., 2019). Students gain

self-confidence, which means that art integration is not only to foster cognitive and psychomotor skills but can also contribute to their overall engagement and how they treat and appreciate others. According to Kisida et al., (2020), arts integration provides students with different ways to learn, which can help fill the gap in learning within the educational system. Art activities and its process become a vibrant and exclusive way to make connections that improve their overall learning experience. Through arts integration, teachers of academic subjects such as Math, History, Science, and English can incorporate elements of the arts into their classrooms as strategies to teach their discipline content (Heiman, 2020). Utilizing arts as part of teaching instruction in non-artistic subjects enhances engagement, fosters creativity, and enriches the overall learning experience. According to Rupnik and Geršak (2022), art has a value and enormous potential in education that that learning through art is just as valuable as learning through science. Both Arts and major subjects offers something unique to a well-rounded and extensive educational experience.

The arts integration serves as an innovative vehicle for students, achieving dual learning objectives while fostering creative connections between art forms and core subjects. Art-based instruction is emphasized, with teachers using art forms creatively to enhance learning in non-artistic subjects. Non-artistic academic subjects must integrate arts to achieve dual objectives; it makes the students understand the subject matter easily and get creative at the same time, which makes the learning meaningful and fun. Learning by doing or hands-on activities through arts integration has been shown to engage students and deepen their understanding of the subject matter. The positive impacts increase student engagement, when integrating art forms such as drawing, music, or drama play, students tend to be excited, more interested, and more involved in learning. Students that are motivated to learn have the willingness to participate and pay attention in class, which keeps them focused and provides them with a positive sense of what they are learning. It promotes the development of 21st-century skills such as critical thinking and creativity. Arts-based instruction not only keeps students interested in the subject matter, but it also boosts their self-efficacy and self-esteem, creating environments that increase their overall engagement and sense of belonging in their classroom and school.

However, there are notable gaps in the existing literature. There are not enough studies or statements on how to exactly integrate the arts into different subject areas of general education courses. Which also limits real-life examples showing how integrating the arts really works in higher education. And lastly, the limitation of information on the impact of arts integration on various types of students inside the classroom, such as those with different learning styles and backgrounds.

Methodology

Respondents

The sampling technique used is purposive sampling technique because the selected respondents are the thirty (30) Teacher Education students enrolled in the Art Appreciation course, a general education course in the Philippine Higher Education. The sampling technique was used to choose and examine a population of a group of people that share a particular characteristic. These individuals may have unique skills, knowledge, and experiences that are essential for understanding how arts integration in general education course impacts learning development.

Instruments

A descriptive correlation design was used in analyzing data to determine if there is a difference between the levels of satisfaction of the respondents on the integration of arts in the general education course of higher education when grouped according to profile. The researchers formulated the questionnaires based on the teaching approach and activities used in the Art Appreciation subject to focus on their relevance to arts integration and their impact on the students' learning progress. The formulated questionnaires are consulted by the research adviser and was validated by research experts to ensure that the questions are aligned with the research objectives.

In interpreting the data statistically and effectively, the scale used by the researchers in evaluating the respondents' level of satisfaction with the given statements were the following:

Scale Value	Mean Range	Satisfaction level in the teaching strategies employed in the Art Appreciation Course
5	4.21 – 5.00	Very Satisfied
4	3.41 – 4.20	Satisfied
3	2.61 – 3.40	Neutral
2	1.81 – 2.60	Dissatisfied
1	1.00 – 1.80	Very Dissatisfied

Procedure

The researchers started the study with reading of various research concepts assigned by the research adviser. The formulated research title and statement of the problem has been approved by the research experts through a panel presentation. Subsequently, the researchers designed a survey questionnaire as the research instrument to assess the satisfaction level of Teacher Education students in the Art Appreciation course regarding the integration of arts in the general education course of higher education. The questionnaire comprises two sections, satisfaction level of the teaching strategies in the Art Appreciation course and the perceived impact of arts integration on cognitive, affective, and psychomotor development. After undergoing research instrument validation through expert validation and

pilot testing to ensure reliability of the instrument, the research adviser allowed the researchers to proceed with the data gathering. The survey was facilitated to the respondents through Google and paper form. Data gathered from answered questionnaires were checked, classified, tabulated, and analyzed according to the research design described in this chapter using Microsoft Excel and JAMOVI statistical tool. A statistician helped the researchers in computing and analyzing the data.

Ethical Considerations

The Center for Research and Development of the school where the researchers were enrolled has an established ethical guidelines and proper procedures that the researchers complied to guarantee their reliability and credibility. The researchers had their research instrument validated by three research experts. The researchers took precautions to protect the respondents' privacy during the data gathering process, and no personal information was gathered. The advisor played a crucial role in ensuring the authenticity and continuous improvement of the students' research. The research was also checked by the research adviser using turnitin to ensure the originality of the context of this study.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. The level of satisfaction of the respondents on the teaching strategies employed in the Art Appreciation course

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Ranking</i>
Learning about arts makes me appreciate the beauty of self-expression.	4.57	Very Satisfied	1
Art exposes me to different cultures and provides me with new perspectives that broaden my understanding of the world.	4.33	Very Satisfied	3
Arts teach me patience, focus, and develop my fine motor skills.	4.2	Satisfied	5.5
Art nurtures my critical thinking skills by analyzing and interpreting various forms of art, such as literature, music, painting, and films.	4.2	Satisfied	5.5
School art activities implemented in non-artistic subjects allow me to understand complex topics with creative insight.	3.83	Satisfied	10
Presentation of arts such as singing, dancing, role-playing, etc., allows me to be myself and boosts my confidence.	4.37	Very Satisfied	2
Arts allow me to convey my ideas through illustrations.	4.16	Satisfied	7
Arts encourage me to express my emotions through performance and written activities.	4.13	Satisfied	8
Visual arts and literacy enhances my ability to interpret and understand visual information.	3.97	Satisfied	9
Arts stimulates my creativity by encouraging me to think outside the box and come up with innovative solutions to issues.	4.23	Very Satisfied	4

Table 1 shows that learning about the arts makes the students appreciate the beauty of self-expression, which ranked first with a weighted mean of 4.57. The presentation of arts such as singing, dancing, role-playing, etc. allows them to be themselves and boosts their confidence. They ranked second with a weighted mean of 4.37. Art provides them with new perspectives that broaden their understanding of the world, ranking 3rd with a weighted mean of 4.33. And lastly, they responded that art stimulates their creativity by thinking outside the box and coming up with innovative solutions, which ranked 4th with a weighted mean of 4.23. The 1st until the 4th ranking indicates that students are very satisfied with the teaching strategies employed in the Art Appreciation course.

However, “Arts teach me patience, focus, and develop my fine motor skills.” And “Art nurtures my critical thinking skills by analyzing and interpreting various forms of art, such as literature, music, painting, and films.” Have the same 5.5 ranking with a weighted mean of 4.2. The students responded that the arts allow them to convey their ideas through illustrations, with a weighted mean of 4.16. They also responded that the arts encourage them to express their emotions through performance and written activities, which ranked 8th with a weighted mean of 4.13. Visual arts and literacy enhance their ability to interpret and understand visual information, which ranked 9th with a weighted mean of 3.97. And lastly, they believe that art activities implemented in non-artistic subjects allow them to understand complex topics with creative insight, which ranked 10 with a weighted mean of 3.83. The 5.5 rank until the 10th ranking indicates that students are satisfied with the teaching strategies employed in the Art Appreciation course.

Therefore, students are very satisfied with the teaching strategies employed in the Art Appreciation course because learning about the arts makes them appreciate the beauty of self-expression. The purpose of art is to create something beautiful and truthful by expressing what we truly feel on the inside (Fatma, 2018). This new understanding corresponds with one’s appreciation of the beauty of self-expression, emphasizing how the arts enable students to break free from barriers and embrace the richness of expressing themselves genuinely without limitations.

Table 2 shows that students in the Art Appreciation course perceive that learning in general education courses can be more interactive if art-based instructional materials are implemented, ranking first with a weighted mean of 4.3. The students can visualize and easily understand concepts through arts integration in general education courses, ranking 2nd with a weighted mean of 4.2. In the higher education general education course, analyzing different art forms, such as music, paintings, and literature, enhances their critical thinking skills and provides new perspectives, ranking 3rd with a weighted mean of 4.1. Through art interpretation, students apply their knowledge to solve problems, ranking 4th with a weighted mean of 4. They perceived that art-based instruction in the higher education

general education course develops their visual-spatial skills to understand visual presentations such as graphs, models, and illustrations, which ranked 5th with a weighted mean of 3.97. However, arts integration allows them to improve their comprehension and language skills, which ranked 6.5 with a weighted mean of 3.9. Arts integration improves their logical thinking skills, with the same rank of 6.5 and a weighted mean of 3.9. Overall, the integration of the arts has shown positive impacts on the students' cognitive development. The students are very satisfied with the impact of arts integration in the higher education curriculum because it improves their comprehension of how to process and understand information and makes their learning fun and interactive.

Cognitive Development

Table 2. *The impact of the integration of arts in the general education course of higher education as perceived by the respondents in terms of Cognitive Development*

Statement	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Ranking
Art-based instructional materials make learning more interactive and easier for me to process information.	4.3	Very Satisfied	1
Art integration can help me recognize patterns (e.g., visual arts, art sequence) that can be used in mathematics and logical thinking.	3.9	Satisfied	6.5
Art-based Instruction develops my visual-spatial skills, which I need to understand visual presentations. (graphs, maps, models, and illustrations)	3.97	Satisfied	5
Creative/artistic activities help me visualize and understand concepts.	4.2	Satisfied	2
Art interpretation teaches us lessons that allow me to apply my knowledge and strategies to solve problems.	4	Satisfied	4
I analyze and criticize different art forms, such as music, painting, pictures, and literature, to enhance my critical thinking skills and to gain new perspective.	4.1	Satisfied	3
I engage myself in arts such as poetry, storytelling, and role-playing to improve my comprehension and language skills.	3.9	Satisfied	6.5

These findings support the study of Silverstein (2020) that when students are engaged in arts integration, they develop their critical thinking skills as they make judgments on how to solve problems. When visual arts are implemented, it allows students to understand ideas in various subjects, such as math and science, which makes them feel good about what they are learning when they work on a problem (Fatma, 2018). Through art-based instructional materials, it fosters the students' creativity, enhances engagement, and helps them gain a deeper understanding of the subject matter.

Affective Development

Table 3. *The impact of the integration of arts in the general education course of higher education as perceived by the respondents in terms of Affective Development*

Statement	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Ranking
Arts integration in the curriculum taps my enthusiasm.	4	Satisfied	5
Interactive art activities are a fun way to promote social interactions and emotional expression that encourage me to cooperate and solve problems with my peers.	4.33	Very Satisfied	1
Artistic activities such as performing, and group presentations build my confidence and self-esteem.	4.06	Satisfied	4
My self-expression and emotional growth are supported by arts integration.	3.77	Satisfied	7
Arts integration activities such as role playing, performances, or group presentations makes me confident in sharing my own ideas with others.	4.1	Satisfied	3
Creative teaching strategies helps me involve interaction with my peers to encourage cooperation and communication to develop positive relationships and social skills.	4.23	Very Satisfied	2
I am exposed to different cultures and their art forms, which promotes cross-cultural perspectives and my empathy for others.	3.9	Satisfied	6

Table 3 shows that arts integration in the general education course of higher education extends beyond the cognitive realms. The students of the Art Appreciation course perceived that art activities promote social interactions and emotional expression, which ranked 1 with a weighted mean of 4.33. Creative teaching strategies develop positive relationships and social skills in the students, which ranked second with a weighted mean of 4.23. In higher education, arts integration activities make students confident in sharing their own ideas with others, ranking 3rd with a weighted mean of 4.1. Through performing and group presentations, it builds the students' confidence and self-esteem, which ranked 4th with a weighted mean of 4.06. Arts integration taps their enthusiasm that aligns with their interests, ranking 5th with a weighted mean of 4. The students perceived that the arts promote cross-cultural perspectives that foster cultural understanding and appreciation and ranked 6th with a weighted mean of 3.9. And lastly, they believe that art integration supports their self-expression, ranking 7th with a weighted mean of 3.77. Overall, the students are very satisfied with the impact of arts integration in the higher education general education course since it contributes to the students' affective development by fostering positive social interactions, empathy for others, and social skills.

Arts integration provides opportunities for students to learn to be open and responsive to diverse perspectives, work respectfully with their peers, and share and accept responsibility (Silverstein, 2023). It promotes the students' emotional expression and a positive relationship. Art activities allow students to participate and collaborate with their peers despite their abilities and culture, which allows them to express their experiences while building empathy and a new perspective on themselves and others (Fatma, 2018). Positive interactions among students foster understanding and connection, promoting emotional expression and nurturing positive relationships.

Psychomotor Development

Table 4. *The impact of the integration of arts in the general education course of higher education as perceived by the respondents in terms of Psychomotor Development*

Statement	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Ranking
Art activities that involve hand movements and body coordination can contribute to the development of my motor skills that are necessary for various tasks such as writing, hands-on activities, and tool use.	4.23	Very Satisfied	2.5
Arts integrated physical activities such as drawing, crafting, and dancing meet my different learning styles and abilities.	4.1	Satisfied	6
Art-based instruction, such as transforming materials into an art piece or to complete puzzles, helps me understand concepts through hands-on activities.	4.23	Very Satisfied	2.5
I engage in physical activities that allow me and my peers to work together and share ideas to promote physical and social development.	4.26	Very Satisfied	1
Art related activities set my mind to think and react-quickly to strengthen the connection of my mind and body.	3.83	Satisfied	7
I express myself through arts such as dancing, singing, performing, or visual presentations to build better connection with my emotion and physical well-being.	4.16	Satisfied	4
The implementation of motor skills activities encourages body awareness, which develops my motor skills and physical fitness.	4.13	Satisfied	5

Table 4 shows that arts integration in higher education and general education plays a crucial role in enhancing students' psychomotor development. The students perceive that physical activities allow them to work together with their peers, which promotes both physical and social development. They ranked first with a weighted mean of 4.26. Engaging in art activities to refine their motor skills through hands-on activities such as puzzles and transforming materials into art pieces ranked 2.25 with a weighted mean of 4.23. Even writing, tool use, and other hand activities refine their motor skills, with the same rank of 2.25 and a weighted mean of 4.23. Through arts performances, students build better connections with their emotions and physical well-being, which ranked 4th with a weighted mean of 4.16. They perceived that when motor skills activities are implemented, it helps them develop motor skills and physical fitness. They ranked 5th with a weighted mean of 4.13. Students perceived those activities such as drawing, crafting, and dancing can meet their different learning styles, ranked 6th with a weighted mean of 4.1. And lastly, art-related activities strengthen the connection between their mind and body, which ranked 7th with a weighted mean of 3.83. Overall, the integration of the arts or art-based approach in the higher education general education course not only enriches their learning experience but also nurtures the students' psychomotor abilities through physical interaction with their peers during hands-on activities and performances that promote both physical and social development.

By combining psychomotor accuracy activities with visual art activities, it can help children develop the coordination of their psychomotor and cognitive skills (Frikha & Alharbi, 2023). Through physical activities, arts integration makes the peers work together and share ideas to achieve both development in physical and social skills.

Table 5. *Test of significant difference on the perceptions of the respondents in the integration of arts in the general education course of higher education when they are grouped according to profile*

Demographic Profile	Group	Mean	SD	t	p	Decision
Program	BEEd	4.20	0.48	1.39	0.175	NS
	BSEd	3.90	0.71			
Demographic Profile	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	p	Decision
Year level	Between Groups	0.31	0.15	0.42	0.662	NS
	Within Groups	9.85	0.37			

The independent sample T-test and ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) are the statistical tools used in this table. The Mean score of the two groups, BEEd with a mean of 4.20 and the BSEd with a mean of 3.90 indicates a numerical favor to the BEEd program. However, the calculated Total of 1.39 with a Percentage of 0.175, alongside the decision of "No Significant Difference". Although the BEEd has a slightly higher Mean score, it is likely due to the gaps of perceptions of the students. Therefore, based on the statistical analysis, when we group the students based on their profiles, there is no significant difference in how they perceive the integration of arts in the general education course of higher education

Conclusions

The outcome of the research emphasizes how integrating arts into general education courses in higher education positively impacts students' learning domains. The purpose of this study is to find out how integrating different art forms into the general education course's teaching strategies can improve students' overall educational experiences. The findings indicate a positive impact of integrating arts into the general education course in higher education, specifically enhancing students' cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains.

The Art Appreciation course's teaching strategies positively affect the students' satisfaction and deepen their appreciation for self-expression through exposure to cultural, historical context, and diverse artistic forms. The study emphasizes the positive impact of arts integration on the cognitive development by making information easier to process through artistic activities and expression, making learning interactive and enjoyable. Affective development benefits from interactive art activities, fostering positive social interactions, emotional expression, and social skills. In terms of psychomotor development, physical activities within the arts contribute to both physical and social growth by encouraging collaboration and idea sharing among students. Additionally, the study discovers no significant differences in students' perceptions of the impact of arts integration when they are grouped according to their profiles. The researchers concluded that integrating arts into general education courses has a wide range of positive impacts on students in all aspects of their development. It emphasizes the role it plays in providing students with an extensive education that accommodates a range of intelligences and learning styles, as well as enabling teachers to develop innovative teaching methods that can enhance student engagement, which also improves student learning outcomes and overall school and student performance.

The researchers recommend providing art activities that will allow students to not only appreciate but also freely express themselves in different art forms to interpret their ideas while ensuring the activities align with the subject matter. By implementing drawing, painting, photography, singing, performing activities, etc., students can interpret ideas through artistic expression. For example, when teaching the history or evolution of education, after teaching the important facts of the lessons, direct the students to create a drawing or poster summarizing the history of the content. It will provide students with a deeper understanding of the content while achieving the objectives of the subject matter and expressing their ideas through arts.

Since art has various forms, the researchers suggest utilizing art to promote an easier way of processing information about the subject matter. Present paintings, cartoons, photography, movies, music, literature, etc. that are connected with the content and direct students to analyze and interpret its meaning to deepen their comprehension and promote interaction. Integrating the arts can foster students' emotional development. The researchers suggest implementing role-playing activities to encourage students to collaborate and build positive relationships with their peers, and poetry writing, or spoken poetry, to encourage self-reflection and expression. Physical activities within arts are an enjoyable way to foster students' psychomotor development while providing opportunities for physical interactions and social development. Here are some activities suggested by the researchers, provide group dance, singing, role-playing, collaborative group projects, and performing art activities that will involve physical and social development.

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